

Studies on Copper (II) Tartrate Complexes—Part-II. Copper (II) Complexes with Tartrate, Ammonia and Substituted ammonia

S. C. SAHOO, S. MISHRA, D. C. DAS and S. PANI

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Jyoti Bihar, Burla-768017, Sambalpur, Orissa

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Two series of copper(II) complexes of the types, $R\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$ and $M\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{TL}$ (where R = substituted ammonium ions, T = tartrate ion, M = sodium, potassium and ammonium ions, and L = ammonia and substituted ammonia) have been studied. The formation of the ion, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{TL}_2$ in solution was established by pH titration. The equilibrium constants of the reactions :

$\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 + \text{L} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{TL}(\text{H}_2\text{O}) + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{TL}(\text{H}_2\text{O}) + \text{L} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{TL}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been determined. The potential features of bonding in the complexes have been discussed from i.r. spectra.

THE sparingly soluble copper(II) tartrate, $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6)$ and the soluble complex salts of the type, $M\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$ (where M = sodium, potassium, and ammonium) have been reported by us earlier¹. Aliphatic amines are weak bases in aqueous solution and can form complex salts of the type, $R\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$ (where R = methyl ammonium, ethyl ammonium etc.). When the aqueous solution of the salts $M\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$ are treated with excess quantity of the corresponding amine (L) another series of complex salts of the type $M\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{TL}$ are formed. The introduction of more amine molecules into the inner sphere of copper(II) ion under higher concentration of amine has been established by pH titration in the present study. When an aqueous solution of $\text{NaCu}(\text{OH})\text{T} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is treated with ammonia (or amines) the water molecules are replaced by stepwise reactions.

The i.r. spectra of the complexes have been studied with a view to explore the potential features of bonding in the complexes.

Materials and Methods

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR (B.D.H.) quality. The starting materials, copper(II) tartrate, $M\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$ were prepared by the method reported earlier¹.

I. Complex salts of the type, $R\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$

(R = methyl, ethyl, diethyl and trimethyl ammonium ions).

Copper(II) tartrate went into solution when it was gently heated with a small quantity of aqueous solution of appropriate amine. It was filtered and

the filtrate was evaporated to dryness over a water bath. The blue crystalline compound obtained was analysed for copper and tartrate content.

II. Complex salts of the type $M\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{TL}$

(M = sodium, potassium, ammonium and substituted ammonium, L = ammonia and substituted ammonia).

An aqueous solution of the complex salt prepared in method I or $M\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$ was treated with the aqueous solution of the appropriate ligand and evaporated to dryness over a water bath. The solid compound thus obtained was again dissolved in small quantity of water and treated with same ligand and evaporated. The compound obtained after repeating the process three to four times was next analysed.

The copper content of the complexes was estimated as copper sulphide and also iodometrically after the complete removal of ammonia or amine. The filtrate obtained after the removal of copper as sulphide was evaporated to dryness over water bath to remove hydrogen sulphide and free hydrochloric acid. The tartaric acid in the residue was estimated by dissolving the residue in water and titrating against standard alkali. The analytical data of the complexes are recorded in Table I.

The conductances of the complexes have been measured for dilute solution (0.001M) by employing Phillips conductivity bridge with a dip type cell. The molecular conductivity data are recorded in Table I. The i.r. spectra of some of the complexes have been taken in potassium bromide phase. The molar conductance values indicate the compounds to be 1 : 1 electrolytes.

Experimental

pH titration

(I) To 25 ml of solution containing 1.002×10^{-3} g.mole of sodium perchlorate, increasing amounts of

TABLE I

Compound	% calculated		% found		Molecular conductance (Λ_m) $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$
	Cu	T	Cu	T	
1. $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$	24.40	56.82	23.93	55.75	157.4
2. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$	23.15	53.91	22.67	51.97	140.1
3. $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$	17.00	39.42	18.05	41.78	127.5
4. $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{NH Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$	22.03	51.31	21.32	50.06	146.0
5. $\text{Na Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T NH}_2\text{CH}_3$	22.03	52.42	21.40	49.87	180.5
6. $\text{Na Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T NH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	21.43	49.92	21.96	49.07	153.9
7. $\text{NH}_4\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T NH}_3$	24.12	56.12	23.92	56.14	153.0
8. $\text{K Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T NH}_2\text{CH}_3$	21.28	49.57	21.53	50.02	135.5
9. $\text{K Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T NH}_3$	22.33	50.01	22.07	49.80	141.3
10. $\text{K Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T NH}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)$	20.33	47.36	20.30	47.33	—
11. $\text{K Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T NH}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$	18.66	43.47	18.88	43.42	—
12. $\text{K Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T N}(\text{CH}_3)_3$	19.45	45.32	19.19	45.56	143.1
13. $\text{K Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$	17.24	40.16	17.19	40.44	154.8
14. $\text{CuT}(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2)_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	22.43	47.86	21.81	50.71	145.0
15. $\text{CuT}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2)_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	19.44	46.32	20.02	47.56	141.6

0.07947M ammonium hydroxide solution was added and the pH was measured by Cambridge Bench pH meter at 26°. The results are graphically represented by curve (A) (Fig. 1) (the pH is plotted against mole

Fig. 1.

ratio i.e., ratio of moles of ligand added to moles of $\text{NaCu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$. In another experiment at the same temperature and the same volume of solution containing 1.002×10^{-3} g.mole of $\text{NaCu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$ was titrated against the same ammonium hydroxide solution. The results are shown in curve (B) (Fig. 1). Similar experiments were performed with other amines.

(II) In another sets of experiments, 100 ml of solution containing 0.001 g.mole of sodium perchlorate and 0.00945 g.mole of ammonium hydroxide

shown in curve (B) (Fig. 2). Similar experiments were performed using other amines.

Results and Discussion

In experiment (I) the pH of the system (B) is lower than that in system (A) for the same volume of ammonium hydroxide added shows that ammonia is removed by $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}^-$ from the solution. At the same pH the distance between the two curves gives the amount of ammonia taken by the complex.

Fig. 2.

was titrated against 0.6384M perchloric acid solution and pH was measured. The results are shown in curve (A) (Fig. 2). In a second experiment, 100 ml. of solution containing 0.001 g.mole of $\text{NaCu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$ and 0.00945 g.mole of ammonium hydroxide was titrated against the same perchloric acid. The results are

$\bar{n}$, the average number of ammonia molecule taken by each $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}^-$ ion is obtained by dividing the amount of ammonia taken, by the amount of $\text{NaCu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$ in the solution. $\bar{n}$ varies from 0 to 2. The concentration of free ammonia in system (B) is calculated in the following manner.

The total amount of ammonia added in system (B)
 $= [\text{NH}_3]_T$

The amount of ammonia taken by the complex
 $= [\text{NH}_3]_B$

The amount of ammonium ion in the solution
 $= [\text{NH}_4^+]$

The amount of free ammonia in the solution
 $= [\text{NH}_3]$

$$[\text{NH}_3]_T = [\text{NH}_3]_B + [\text{NH}_4^+] + [\text{NH}_3]$$

or
$$[\text{NH}_3]_T - [\text{NH}_3]_B = [\text{NH}_4^+] + [\text{NH}_3]$$

or
$$\text{NH}_3 = \frac{[\text{NH}_3]_T - [\text{NH}_3]_B}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]} \quad \dots (3)$$

where, K is the equilibrium constant of the reaction,

The value of K is determined from the direct titration of ammonia against perchloric acid in experiment (II) and used for calculation of $[\text{NH}_3]$. The equilibrium constants K_1 and K_2 are obtained from the formation curve, $\bar{n}$ is plotted against $\log \frac{1}{[\text{NH}_3]}$ and $\log K_1$

and $\log K_2$ are obtained corresponding to $\bar{n} = 0.5, 1$ and 1.5 respectively. The values with those of other systems are collected in Table 2.

The ratio of K_1 and K_2 is small in all these cases and hence the values obtained are approximate values which are corrected by Schroder method². The corrected values are also recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Ligand solution	Equilibrium constants from formation curve		Correct equilibrium constants by Schroder method	
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2
NH_3	3.24	2.67	2.52 ± 0.18	3.38 ± 0.18
CH_3NH_2	3.38	2.37	3.23 ± 0.18	2.52 ± 0.18
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$	3.42	2.36	3.29 ± 0.18	2.49 ± 0.18
$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH}$	3.04	2.39	2.56 ± 0.25	2.87 ± 0.25
$(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}$	3.65	2.77	3.43 ± 0.25	2.99 ± 0.25
$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}$	3.30	2.37	2.85 ± 0.25	2.81 ± 0.25

It is of interest to note that in the ammonia system the corrected value of K_2 is greater, whereas in other case it is less. This means that the six co-ordination complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$, $(\text{NH}_3)_3^-$ is preferred to the five coordination complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T} \cdot (\text{NH}_3)^-$. In case of other complexes the ligands enter in stepwise reaction probably due to the presence of alkyl groups in the ligand.

In experiment-II, the two curves (A) and (B) very nearly coincide till one third of the ammonia

is neutralised by the acid. After that the two curves diverge and the pH of the system (B) is lower than that of the system (A) for the same amount of acid added. This means that the amount of free ammonia in the system (B) is less, due to complex formation. The amount of ammonia bound to the complex can be determined as follows. As a first approximation it is assumed that the acid added reacts completely with ammonia to give ammonium ion in both the systems, consequently the reaction (1) and (2) in the system (B) proceed in the reverse direction. Let A and B be two points on curve (A) and (B) respectively cut by the same pH axis. The concentration of total amount of ammonia at A and B are represented by $[\text{NH}_3]_T^A$ and $[\text{NH}_3]_T^B$. The concentrations of other constituents at A and B are represented by $[\]_A$ and $[\]_B$ respectively.

$$[\text{NH}_4^+]_A = [\text{HClO}_4]_A$$

$$[\text{NH}_4^+]_B = [\text{HClO}_4]_B$$

$$[\text{NH}_3]_T^A = [\text{NH}_4^+]_A + [\text{NH}_3]_A$$

Since certain amount of ammonia is bound to the complex at B, the amount of free ammonia at B, $[\text{NH}_3]_B$ is obtained as follows. At the same pH

$$\frac{[\text{NH}_3]_A}{[\text{NH}_4^+]_A} = \frac{[\text{NH}_3]_B}{[\text{NH}_4^+]_B} \quad \dots (5)$$

In the above equation except $[\text{NH}_3]_B$ the other quantities are known. Hence $[\text{NH}_3]_B$ is calculated by equation (5). The amount of ammonia bound to the complex is given by :

$$[\text{NH}_3] \text{ Bound} = [\text{NH}_3]_T^B - ([\text{NH}_4^+]_B + [\text{NH}_3]_B) \quad \dots (6)$$

$\bar{n}$ the average number of ammonia bound to each $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}^-$ ion is obtained by dividing $[\text{NH}_3]$ bound by $[\text{NaCu}(\text{OH})\text{T}]$. $\bar{n}$ is plotted against $\log \frac{1}{[\text{NH}_3]}$

and $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ obtained from this curve are respectively 2.37 and 1.57. These values do not agree with those obtained by direct titration method. The lower values obtained due to some other reactions taking place with acid simultaneously.

In the system (A) ammonia is completely neutralised when 14.8 ml of perchloric acid is added and the pH rapidly comes down when the end point is exceeded. In the system (B) also this decreases after addition of 14.8 ml of perchloric acid but the fall of pH is less rapid indicating another reaction to be taking place at lower pH. The probable reaction is,

For the calculation of the equilibrium constant of reaction (7) it is assumed that all the ammonia present in the system (B) is completely neutralised when 14.8 ml of perchloric acid is added. Acid excess above this amount reacts with $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}^-$ to

give $\text{CuT}(\text{Sol})$. The equilibrium constant of the reaction (7) is calculated as follows. Excess of acid above that required for neutralisation of ammonia = $[\text{HClO}_4]_E$. The amount of hydrogen ion taken by $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}^- = [\text{HClO}_4]_E - [\text{H}^+]$. The amount of hydrogen ion in the solution is calculated from the pH . The average number of protons taken by $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}^-$ is given by :

$$\frac{[\text{HClO}_4]_E - [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{NaCu}(\text{OH})\text{T}]} = \bar{n}$$

$\bar{n}$ is plotted against pH and at $\bar{n} = 0.5 \log k$ is found to be 6.25. Patel, Satpathy and Pari have reported pK of the reverse reaction to be 5.59. This difference might be due to the existence of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}(\text{NH}_3)^-$ after the addition of required amount of acid to neutralise ammonia.

The i.r. spectra of a few complexes are recorded in table 3.

TABLE 3

Compound	Absorption bands in cm^{-1}
$\text{NH}_4\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T} \cdot \text{NH}_3$	1600 1375 1110 and 1055 430
$\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T} \cdot \text{NH}_4\text{CH}_3$	1610 1365 1105 and 1060 440
$\text{NaCu}(\text{OH})\text{T} \cdot \text{NH}_4\text{CH}_3$	1605 1365 1105 and 1055 444
$\text{CH}_3\text{NH Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}$	1605 1370 1105 and 1055

Krischner and Keisling have reported³ sharp absorption bands at 1750 and 1097 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of *d*-tartaric acid. The former has been assigned to the carboxylic acid groups and the latter to the C-O stretching of the secondary alcoholic groups. In sodium potassium tartrate a strong band and a medium band are observed at 1615 cm^{-1} and 1460 cm^{-1} respectively. These are due to symmetric and antisymmetric vibration of the carboxylate groups. In these compounds a strong and sharp band is observed at 1610 to 1600 cm^{-1} but no band is observed at about 1460 cm^{-1} . This indicates that both the carboxylate groups are coordinated. Goulden has reported⁴ that in lactate the secondary alcoholic groups has an inplane O-H bonding absorption band at 1275 cm^{-1} which is shifted to 1390 cm^{-1} upon chelation of secondary alcoholic group. The band at 1365 to 1375 cm^{-1} in these compounds might be due to chelation of alcoholic

group. Instead of a single band at about 1097 cm^{-1} as reported for *d*-tartaric acid a split band at 1110 and 1055 cm^{-1} is observed in all the complexes, which indicates that the two secondary alcoholic groups are different. This means that one of the two alcoholic groups is coordinated. The absorption band observed at about 500 cm^{-1} in cobalt(III) amines has been assigned to Co(III)-N stretching frequency by Powell and Sheppard⁶ and also Nakamoto⁶. Shimanouchi and Nakagawa⁷ made a normal coordinate analysis of the $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{3+}$ ion and assigned to the Co-N stretching mode a weak band at 464 cm^{-1} . In the present study weak bands are found in the region 430-444 cm^{-1} in a few cases. These absorption bands are most probably due to Cu-N stretching mode. The structure of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}^-$ ion can be represented by :

There might be a coordinated water molecule in the complex and is replaced by another ligand in $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})\text{T}^-$.

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